

How Metaverse might have an impact on user experience

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Abstract

Metaverse is an interactive virtual environment connected to the physical world through immersive technologies in which users can perform everyday tasks. Immersive technologies erase boundaries between the physical and virtual worlds and allow users to experience the feeling of immersion. It is an environment based on core technologies such as web 3.0, blockchain, cryptocurrencies, non-fungible tokens (NFTs) and artificial intelligence (AI), and immersive technologies such as virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), mixed reality (MR), extended reality (XR). However, even though the metaverse is not a new concept, user experience (UX) designers have to design the user experience well in order to make it as intuitive as possible. The paper reflects on main features of the metaverse, such as the design and appearance of the environment, digital identity of its users, accessibility and inclusivity, and interaction. The aim of this paper is to examine the expectations and attitudes of students in the field of information sciences (IS) and employees in the IT field regarding: a) the role of UX designers in the creation of the metaverse; b) the design and appearance of the environment, that is, the nature of activities and interactions in the metaverse; and c) the adaptation of the metaverse to users' expectations and needs. The research is based on the following research questions: a) How do students in the IS field and employees in the IT field perceive the role of UX designers in creating interactive virtual environments like the metaverse? b) What are the expectations of students in the IS field and employees in the IT field regarding the design and appearance of the metaverse environment? c) What are the views and opinions of students in the IS field and employees in the IT field about the potential impact of the metaverse on activities (work, education, entertainment, etc.) and interaction? The research was conducted through the LimeSurvey online questionnaire consisting of 24 closed questions. The questionnaire was conducted via e-mail and social media in October and November 2022, and statistical analysis was performed with SPSS. The respondents are students in

the field of information sciences at the Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, University of Osijek, Croatia and employees of IT companies in Osijek, Croatia. Majority (63.8%) of respondents agreed that the role of UX designer will change with the arrival of the metaverse. Respondents expect that metaverse will have well-thought-out design, especially for users with disabilities. The interaction in the metaverse will occur between avatars and will entail a more complex level of interacting with the environment. Furthermore, the idea and concept of metaverse is quite ambiguous. Respondents believe that the biggest advantages of the metaverse imply connecting the world despite the physical distance. On the other hand, the biggest disadvantages include the loss of connection with the physical world.

Keywords: immersive technologies; interaction design; metaverse; user experience

Introduction

We are witnessing the accelerated development of technology and it is necessary to monitor its invention and diffusion. We are currently using Web 2.0, a web that is characterised by interaction with the user but is increasingly dynamic and complex. Web 3.0, also called the semantic web, is still being developed using the concepts of blockchain technology and decentralisation, and it will make data machine-readable. There is also artificial intelligence (AI), which is becoming more advanced every day, as well as Internet of Things (IoT) and edge computing. Also, immersive technologies such as virtual (VR) and augmented reality (AR) have been popular for a long time. From the perspective of user experience (UX) design all these technologies should be monitored and adjusted to users' needs and wants. Therefore, the role of a UX designer is no longer as simple as before.

In the first part of the paper the concept of metaverse will be described. Though it consists of two types of technologies - basic and immersive technologies - the emphasis in this paper is put on immersive technology and its experience which gives the user a sense of a new reality. The second part analyses the UX in general and its aspects in the metaverse, such as environment design, digital identity, accessibility and inclusion, interaction and communication, and gamification. All these aspects of UX should be acknowledged by the designer during the design process. Furthermore, the potential advantages and disadvantages of the metaverse in regards to UX are mentioned. Some of the advantages could be immersive experiences, new business opportunities, and the advancement of learning and education. Disadvantages can include cybercrime, virtual bullying or even mental health issues. The third and central part of this paper provides an overview of the research conducted in October and November 2022 in regards to interrelation between the emerging technology of the metaverse and UX.

Metaverse: Definition, description and main features

Metaverse is an interactive virtual environment connected to the physical world through immersive technologies where users can do everyday things. The term is not new; it has been around for 30 years and was coined by author Neal Stephenson in his 1992 book *Snow Crash* to describe the virtual world of the future. Stephenson sees the metaverse as a massive virtual environment similar to the physical world where users interact through avatars, and

his vision later inspired famous innovators such as Mark Zuckerberg and Jeff Bezos, as well as many others (Lee et al., 2021).

Metaverse includes technologies that can be divided into two groups. The first group are core technologies including web 3.0, blockchain, cryptocurrencies, non-fungible tokens (NFTs), and AI (Queppelin, 2022). Web 3.0 is the next iteration of the World Wide Web that will give users more control over their data and content, and decentralisation plays an important role

(Network Encyclopedia, 2022). In regards to the issue of decentralisation, the blockchain technology will help facilitate greater distribution, collaboration, interoperability, participation and re-democratization of the Internet. It is a shared collection of records that facilitates the process of transactions, data storage, and the tracking of assets in a network (IBM, 2022). Data is stored in the form of blocks stacked one after the other, and once added to the chain, the block and transaction cannot be modified (Queppelin, 2022). The next technology is cryptocurrencies, which form the foundation of the digital economy. Every transaction in the metaverse will be done through cryptocurrency. Related to cryptocurrencies are NFTs, unique digital assets on the blockchain that are bought and sold with cryptocurrencies. The last technology is AI, which has a great impact on the virtual world because it makes users more sensitive to their actions in VR, and their experience more realistic. It is also the link between the first and second groups of metaverse technologies (Queppelin, 2022).

The second group are immersive technologies. Immersive technology is a technology that erases boundaries between the physical and virtual world and allows users to experience the feeling of immersion. Immersive technologies like 360, AR, VR, MR and XR are key technologies in developing the metaverse. 360 is the basic and probably the most well-known immersive technology and examples of 360 immersive experiences can often be found on social media. AR allows the user to observe a certain entity or object as a computer-generated content that doesn't exist in the physical space. VR is a simulated 3D environment that provides immersive experience and it can be identical or completely different from the user's physical environment. Mixed Reality (MR) is a combination of AR and VR, while Extended Reality (XR) combines all three realities and is the concept closest to the metaverse (Kumawat et al., 2020).

There are several types of metaverse. The most famous one is the project of Mark Zuckerberg's metaverse, which he presented in October 2021. However, a few months later Neal Stephenson started working on his metaverse Lamina1. Besides them, there are a number of metaverse projects, such as Decentraland, The Sandbox, Second Life, Genesis World, Gather.town and others.

User experience of metaverse

The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) defines UX as "a person's perceptions and reactions resulting from the use or anticipated use of a product, system or service." (ISO, 2022) The term was coined by Don

Norman, co-founder of the Nielsen Norman Group. UX design is the process by which a design team creates a product to provide the user with a pleasant, relevant, and intuitive experience. UX designer creates solutions that eliminate product pain points while emphasising user satisfaction and product efficiency. Tasks may vary, but often include user research, creating user personas, designing wireframes and prototypes and usability testing (The Interaction Design Foundation, 2022). With the development of new technologies and the arrival of a new iteration of the web, UX designers must adapt their design to make the user experience more intuitive. In addition to mobile devices, computers, and their components, the UX increasingly includes VR equipment. Hence, there are a few aspects of UX design that should be taken into consideration, especially in the context of building the virtual world of metaverse. Of course, certain advantages and disadvantages of metaverse should also be addressed.

Environment design

There are several important issues to consider when designing the virtual environment. First, when positioning the content, it is important to remember that users have physical limitations and a limited field of vision, so it is necessary to organise the spatial environment in order to increase its efficiency. Second, users should be able to customise the app according to personal preferences. Also, the design should be adapted to experienced and inexperienced users. Thirdly, the user must feel physically comfortable and comfortable within the environment, so one should be careful when planning and designing the process of interaction and should use simple and relevant elements that do not distract the user from what is important, while reducing the levels of frustration. Fourth, designers should make the virtual experience as engaging as possible through use of visual, audio, and narrative elements. Fifth, the design of the virtual environment should be as similar as possible to the nature of the real, physical world. Finally, the designer should allow the user to provide feedback using interaction, as well as easily undo actions (Vi et al., 2019).

Digital identity

An avatar is a digital representation of a user in the metaverse and an important part of his/hers ability to communicate with others and interact with the virtual environment. As a virtual embodiment it is an important part of the experience of immersion, i.e. having real experience that affects the person behind the avatar (Teräs, 2015). They can also be used to display a user's personality, identity and likeness. Users control avatars, including their appearance and behaviour. Main characteristics of an avatar are its ability to provide strong feeling of immersion in the virtual environment and feeling of presence, ability to offer (true or fictional) digital representation of the person, and its ability to provide the person with different possibilities of interaction and communication within the virtual world (Babich, 2022).

Accessibility and inclusion

Due to the competitiveness between different tech companies in their attempt to gain an advantage in the market, accessibility issues could be deprioritised when the first version of the metaverse is launched. For hearing-

impaired users, being able to move and orient in the metaverse means there will need to exist a certain type of spatial description system. Blind and visually impaired users will need to have their screen reading capabilities adapted and translated to audio descriptions and instructions. And for users who suffer from anxiety or sensory processing disorders (SPD), system functionality will need to be adjusted in order to reduce noise, sounds and other stimuli thus providing more calm and balanced sensory experience of the virtual environment, especially in regards to issues of interoception, proprioception, nociception (Alexiou, 2022; Devin, 2021).

Interaction and communication

The user in the metaverse is more active than ever because interaction is no longer just about sharing photos or links. The user is now a "player" and everything he does has a reaction.

It is important that every interaction appears as natural as possible and that the virtual world is as similar as possible to the physical world. The user can maintain the interaction through gestures, voice, controller, etc. The interaction cannot be paused as in video games because it is maintained in real time. Furthermore, the metaverse will open a new chapter in human communication. Hundreds or even millions of people will be able to participate in a shared experience, such as a concert, in sync. Users will be able to see and interact with everyone who joins the virtual event (Babich, 2022.).

Gamification

Metaverse is not only an evolution of the Internet, but also a new way of creating and shaping content, the success of which will depend on how well it motivates users to interact with the existing content and generate new content. Metaverse designers can rely on tried and tested game mechanics such as *Massive Multiplayer Online Video Games* whose most valuable sources of mechanics generate excellent user engagement and response making users engaged in the virtual space for hours on end. Therefore, the metaverse can adopt tactics like "play-to-earn" (the more time users spend in the system, the more coins (virtual or crypto currencies) they have), rewarding contribution (users get benefits by contributing content to services, e.g. the best player badge) and completing game-like objectives (users perform virtual tasks in exchange for coins) (Babich, 2022).

Advantages and disadvantages of metaverse

Some of the advantages of the metaverse are the possibility to connect, interact and collaborate with one another despite physical distance, deeper and greater immersive experiences, new business opportunities, advancement of learning and education, positive impact on cryptocurrencies, new opportunities for financial gain, improvement of the work environment, etc.. On the other hand, there may be various disadvantages, such as cybercrime, negative impact on culture and society, psychological manipulation, addiction issues, loss of connection with the physical world, privacy and security issues, mental health issues, virtual bullying, hardware issues and legislation.

Research

The aim and purpose of the research

The aim of this paper is to examine the expectations and attitudes of potential metaverse users coming from the field of IS (students) and IT (employees) regarding their future and possible user experience of the metaverse. In particular, the aim is to examine their expectations and attitudes regarding: a) the role of UX design(ers) in the creation of the metaverse, b) the design and appearance of metaverse environment, and c) the adaptation of the metaverse to users' needs and wants. This study is based on the following research questions:

- How do students in the IS field and employees in the IT field perceive the role of UX designers in creating interactive virtual environments like the metaverse?
- What are the expectations of students in the IS field and employees in the IT field regarding the design and appearance of the metaverse environment?
- What are the views and opinions of students in the IS field and employees in the IT field about the potential impact of the metaverse on activities (work, education, entertainment, etc.) and interaction?

Methodology and respondents

The research was conducted from October 28th to November 6th 2022 using the online questionnaire LimeSurvey which consisted of 24 closed questions, and the data was processed using the statistical tool SPSS. The survey was distributed via social network Facebook and communication tool Slack. The respondents were students of information sciences at the Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences in Osijek and employees of IT companies in Osijek. There were 131 responses in the survey, of which 94 were valid.

The sample was composed of 94 respondents. 59.6% participants were male and 40.4% were female. 30.9% of respondents are between 18 and 24 years old, 36.2% of respondents are between 25 and 30 years old, and 29.8% of respondents are between 31 and 40 years old. The majority of respondents (84.4%) come from Eastern Croatia, of which 60.6% are from the city of Osijek. 29% of respondents belong to the student population, and 71% are employees. Also, 77.7% work in the IT sector, of which 71% are employees and 6.1% are student population. The most common jobs of the respondents are UX/UI designer (20.5%), mobile developer (13%), frontend developer (8.6%), project manager (7.6%) and quality assurance (QA) (6.5%). The results of the survey provide answers to the stated research questions.

Results

The first group of questions was related to the issue of immersive technologies. Regarding the question "Do you have experience using immersive technologies?" 40.4% of respondents answered that they have, while 59.6% of respondents answered that they have no experience. When asked a question "What prevents you from accepting this type of gaming/entertainment?" almost half (46.4%) of the respondents who have no experience with immersive

technologies, stated that they were not interested in it. 78.9% of the respondents who have experience in immersive technologies answered that they also have experience in gaming and 10.5% of them use immersive technology every day.

Graph 1. Purpose for joining the metaverse

The second group of questions was related to the use-cases (applications) of the metaverse. In question "For what purposes would you join the metaverse?" 12 metaverse applications were offered and it was possible to choose multiple answers. As shown in Graph 1, the majority of respondents (57.4%) would use the metaverse for entertainment purposes, while the smallest number of respondents (1.1%) would join for political and activism purposes. Respondents stated that they were generally interested in all the applications proposed. When asked "Which of the following metaverse projects are you familiar with?", where projects such as Decentraland, The Sandbox and Second Life were offered, more than half of the respondents (58.5%) stated they were not familiar with any of the projects.

Table 1. Respondents' views on user experience in the metaverse

	Statement	Mean
Environment design	The concept of the metaverse doesn't seem intuitive to me.	3,07
Environment design	I expect that metaverse will have the ability to notify users of potential dangers and consequences.	4,04
Digital identity	I expect the user to be able to express their own unique style and personality by changing their avatar's body shape and clothing.	4,26
Accessibility and inclusivity	I expect that in the metaverse, hearing impaired people will always have subtitles in front of them, preferably in real time.	4,01
Accessibility and inclusivity	I expect that interactive interfaces will make the metaverse more accessible to people with sensory disabilities.	4,00
Interaction and communication	I expect that the interaction in the metaverse will not be reduced to clicking and swiping, but will go to a higher level - looking, touching and moving the body with 3D objects.	4,05
Interaction and communication	I expect that the way users interact and explore the environment will depend heavily on the equipment they use.	4,09
Interaction and communication	I expect interaction (whether between avatars or objects) to take place through visual, acoustic, haptic, olfactory and gustatory channels.	4,07
Gamification	I expect metaverse users to have a map with POIs (point of interest) they can navigate.	3,99

The third group of questions was related to the user experience of the metaverse and was divided into five subtopics: environment design, digital identity, accessibility and inclusiveness, the nature of interaction and communication, and gamification. Respondents were able to express how much they agree or disagree with the particular statements through a 5 point Likert scale (from complete disagreement (1) to complete agreement (5)). Table 1 shows the results where the respondents agreed the most with a specific statement (arithmetic average).

The next question was "Do you think the metaverse will change the role of UX designers?" to which more than half (63.8%) of respondents answered affirmatively.

Respondents had to justify their answers, and these are some of the explanations:

- “I believe that no one wants the world to become a Black Mirror episode, but we are fast approaching that moment, as the questions in this questionnaire confirm. In that context, I think the role of the metaverse designer is to walk a fine line. On the one hand, (if they constantly think about their design decisions) they will put up fences so that we don't enter the world of dystopia, and on the other hand, they will develop that same world and try to attract an increasing number of users to it.”
- “The new medium brings with it new rules and possibilities, new UX patterns, so the role will not be the same. UX designers will perhaps be more important than they are now.”
- “UX designers will have to get more and more into the psychology of the individual. There will be more division of labour in the field of UX design.”
- “I don't think it's going to change much because I don't believe the Metaverse will ever come to life, or at least I hope not.”

Graph 2. Advantages of metaverse

The fourth group of questions related to the advantages and disadvantages of the metaverse. As shown in Graph 2, in regards to the question "What do you perceive as the greatest advantage of the metaverse?" almost half (45.7%) of respondents agreed that it is its ability to connect the world despite the physical distance, and the lowest number (2.1%) agreed that it is its capacity to improve the working environment.

Graph 3. Disadvantages of metaverse

When asked "What do you perceive as the biggest disadvantage of the metaverse?" most respondents (41.5%) answered "loss of connection with the physical world", and the lowest number of respondents (2.1%) answered "privacy and security". All answers are shown in Graph 3.

Discussion and conclusion

Metaverse is an interactive virtual environment connected to the physical world through immersive technologies where users can do everyday things. As stated earlier, it is not a new concept, but it is becoming an increasingly popular one, so it is necessary to think about how to apply the best design approach and make the user experience as intuitive as possible.

This paper provides answers to previously stated research questions. Most IS students and employees in the IT field believe that the role of UX designers will change because the metaverse represents a new way of thinking and creating virtual environments and interactions. We can no longer think about *mouse-clicking* on the screen when the screen as such will no longer exist. Respondents also believe that new technologies come with new rules, opportunities and challenges, so the role of the UX designer will not be the same, moreover, it will be more important than ever. The user experience will also change, but it won't be very intuitive, at least anytime soon. The issue of metaverse user experience can be divided into five topics: environment design, digital identity, accessibility and inclusiveness, interaction and communication, and gamification. What can be expected in environment design is that *well-thought-out* design will reduce the nausea or anxiety induced by immersive technologies. Respondents expect that metaverse will have the ability to inform users about potential dangers and consequences. Furthermore, the user will be able to express his own unique style and personality in the metaverse by changing and controlling his avatar's body, appearance and behaviour. Respondents also expect that metaverse will be adjusted to users with disabilities, e.g. hearing-impaired people will always have subtitles in front of them, preferably in real time. They also expect

interactive interfaces to make the metaverse more accessible to people with sensory disabilities. The interaction in the metaverse will occur between avatars and will not be reduced to clicking and swiping, but will entail a more complex level of interacting with the environment and other users – viewing, touching and moving the body with 3D objects. However, the way users interact and explore the environment can depend heavily on the equipment they use. Interaction (either between avatars or objects) can take place through visual, acoustic, olfactory and gustatory channels. In the end, all that experience will seem gamified, and users could have a map with points of interest through which they can navigate in the virtual environment. Another thing to remember is that the idea and concept of metaverse is quite ambiguous. Respondents believe that the biggest advantages of the metaverse imply connecting the world despite the physical distance, having immersive experience and improving work and education experience. On the other hand, the biggest disadvantages include the loss of connection with the physical world, the negative impact on culture and society, and the negative impact on mental health.

In conclusion, with the arrival of a new iteration of the web comes a change in the user experience. UX designers must be ready for a new perspective of design because the question is when the metaverse will take its full form. Today, NFT and cryptocurrencies are already popular, which are part of the metaverse, and the puzzle is slowly being completed. It can be assumed that equipment for immersive technology will therefore become more available and cheaper. Although the metaverse has many advantages, not everyone will embrace it. Some people don't like the idea of virtual reality. Finally, it is only a matter of time before the metaverse becomes our digital reality.

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Suggested citation to this article:

Maurus, E. & Puhek, A. (2023). How Metaverse Might Have An Impact On User Experience. *Proceedings of the BOBCATSSS 2023: A New Era - Exploring the Possibilities and Expanding the Boundaries*, Oslo Metropolitan University (OsloMet), Oslo, Norway, January 25-27, 2023.
